

Health Anxiety and Attitudes Toward Complementary and Alternative Medicine in Adults: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study aimed to examine the relationship between health anxiety and attitudes toward complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) among adults attending a university hospital and to explore differences according to sociodemographic and health-related variables.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between September and November 2023 with adults aged 18 years and older who attended outpatient clinics at Harran University Hospital and agreed to participate (n = 164). Data were collected using a Personal Information Form, the Health Anxiety Scale (HAS), and the Holistic Complementary and Alternative Medicine Questionnaire (HCAMQ). Descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation analyses were performed. Statistical significance was set at $p < .05$.

Results: The mean age of participants was 35.7 ± 8.85 years; most were female (86.6%) and university graduates (75.6%). The mean total HAS score was 14.29 ± 6.45 . The mean total HCAMQ score was 28.96 ± 8.42 . Education level was significantly associated with total HAS and bodily vigilance scores ($p < .05$). Mental health status showed significant associations with all HAS and HCAMQ scores ($p < .001$). Significant negative correlations were observed between total HAS and total HCAMQ ($r = -.812, p = .019$), holistic health beliefs ($r = -.664, p = .034$), and CAM orientation ($r = -.927, p = .007$). As lower HCAMQ scores reflect more positive CAM attitudes, higher health anxiety was associated with greater CAM orientation.

Conclusion: Increased health anxiety is linked to more favorable attitudes toward CAM. Routine assessment of CAM use and targeted psychoeducational interventions may benefit individuals with elevated health anxiety.

Keywords: Health Anxiety, Complementary and Alternative Medicine, Attitudes, University Hospital, Cross-Sectional Study

INTRODUCTION

Health anxiety is a psychological condition characterized by the misinterpretation of bodily sensations, whereby mild or normal physical symptoms are perceived as indicators of a serious illness, leading to excessive distress (1). This condition is associated with heightened somatic vigilance and an intensified perception of threat (2). Although historically conceptualized under the term “hypochondriasis,” contemporary cognitive-behavioral models emphasize that health anxiety is maintained through maladaptive cognitive appraisals and safety-seeking behaviors (3).

With the widespread use of the internet, health anxiety has acquired an additional dimension referred to as “cyberchondria.” Easy access to online health information—often unreliable or misinterpreted—may exacerbate anxiety levels in vulnerable individuals (4). Individuals with elevated health anxiety frequently engage in repeated medical consultations and diagnostic testing, or conversely, may avoid healthcare settings altogether (5).

Complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a broad range of health care practices that fall outside the conventional biomedical system but may constitute part of traditional health practices in certain cultures (6). CAM includes modalities such as herbal remedies, acupuncture, massage, meditation, yoga, and homeopathy, and generally aims to promote holistic well-being (7). In Türkiye, culturally rooted CAM practices such as prayer, herbal therapies, cupping therapy (hijama), and other traditional methods are commonly used (8).

Attitudes toward CAM are influenced by various factors, including age, gender, educational level, cultural beliefs, illness perceptions, and health-seeking behaviors (9, 10). Previous research suggests that some individuals may turn to CAM in order to gain a greater sense of control over their health, take a more active role in treatment decisions, and manage uncertainty related to illness (11). This tendency appears particularly pronounced

among individuals with chronic illnesses or medically unexplained symptoms (12).

The growing interest in CAM cannot be attributed solely to cultural factors; it may also reflect perceived limitations of conventional medicine in fully addressing patients’ expectations and subjective experiences. However, unregulated or inappropriate use of CAM may pose significant health risks. Therefore, understanding individuals’ attitudes toward CAM, the psychological factors underlying these attitudes, and their levels of health anxiety is of considerable importance for clinical practice (13).

Although previous studies have shown that individuals with chronic illnesses, anxiety-related symptoms, or medically unexplained complaints may be more likely to use CAM, limited research has directly examined the relationship between health anxiety and attitudes toward CAM in general outpatient populations. In addition, despite the widespread use of culturally rooted CAM practices in Türkiye, the psychological factors underlying these attitudes remain insufficiently understood.

In this context, examining the relationship between health anxiety and attitudes toward CAM may contribute to improved clinical decision-making processes and support the development of more integrative, patient-centered approaches to healthcare. Accordingly, the present study aims to investigate the association between health anxiety levels and attitudes toward complementary and alternative medicine among adults attending a university hospital.

METHOD

Study Design and Aim

This study was designed as a descriptive, cross-sectional investigation aiming to determine the relationship between individuals’ levels of health anxiety and their attitudes toward complementary and alternative medicine (CAM).

Setting and Time Frame

The study was conducted at Harran University Hospital between September and November 2023.

Population and Sample

The study population consisted of patients who attended outpatient clinics at Harran University Hospital for various reasons during the study period (September–November 2023). A total of 164 individuals who met the inclusion criteria and agreed to participate were included in the study. No a priori power analysis was performed; however, the final sample size was considered adequate for the planned statistical analyses. A non-probability convenience sampling method was used. All individuals who met the eligibility criteria and agreed to participate during the study period were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants were required to:

- Have attended any outpatient clinic of the hospital during the study period;
- Be 18 years of age or older;
- Have no hearing, speech, or cognitive impairments that would prevent completion of the data collection instruments;
- Provide voluntary consent to participate.

Data Collection Instruments

Data were collected using a Personal Information Form, the Health Anxiety Scale (HAS), and the Holistic Complementary and Alternative Medicine Questionnaire (HCAMQ).

Personal Information Form

The Personal Information Form was developed by the researchers and consisted of 11 items assessing participants' sociodemographic characteristics, including age, gender, marital status, family structure, educational level, occupation, and perceived economic status.

Health Anxiety Scale (HAS)

The Health Anxiety Scale was developed by Salkovskis et al. (2002) and consists of 18 self-report items (2). Each item is rated on a 4-point scale (0–3), with higher scores indicating greater levels of health anxiety. The Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Aydemir et al. (2013) (14). In the Turkish adaptation, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was reported as 0.918, with item–total

correlations ranging from 0.405 to 0.769. The test–retest reliability coefficient was $r = 0.572$.

Holistic Complementary and Alternative Medicine Questionnaire (HCAMQ)

The HCAMQ was developed by Hyland et al. (2003) and validated in Türkiye by Erci (2007) (8, 15). The instrument consists of 11 Likert-type items assessing attitudes toward CAM and includes two subscales: Complementary and Alternative Medicine Orientation and Holistic Health Beliefs. Total scores range from 11 to 66, with lower scores indicating more positive attitudes toward CAM. In the present study, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.71.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. For normally distributed variables, mean \pm standard deviation values were reported; for non-normally distributed variables, median (minimum–maximum) values were provided. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

When comparing two groups, independent samples t-tests were used. For comparisons involving more than two groups, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted. The relationship between scale scores was evaluated using Pearson correlation analysis. A p-value of $< .05$ was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Harran University with the approval number E-76244175-050.01.01-172343. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Prior to participation, all individuals were informed about the purpose, procedures, voluntary nature of participation, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the research process. No personally identifiable information was collected, and all data were analyzed and reported in aggregate form. Data were stored

securely and accessed only by the research team.

RESULTS

The findings obtained from the analysis of the research data are presented in this section. Sociodemographic and selected personal characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1. The mean age of the participants was 35.7 ± 8.85 years, with ages ranging from 20 to 61 years.

The majority of the participants were female (86.6%), married (76.8%), university graduates (75.6%), and living in nuclear family structures (86.6%). Most participants reported having a moderate economic status (70.7%). In terms of perceived health status, 50.0% rated their mental health as good, while 52.4% reported good physical health. Regarding leisure activities, 37.8% of participants indicated that they preferred reading books in their free time.

Table 1. Some characteristics of the participants

Characteristics	Mean \pm SD	Median (Min-Max)
Age	$35,7 \pm 8,85$	35 (20 - 61)
Characteristics	n	%
Gender	Male	22, 13,4
	Female	142, 86,6
Education status	Primary education	8, 4,9
	High school	32, 19,5
	University	124, 75,6
Marital status	Married	126, 76,8
	Single	38, 23,2
Family type	Nuclear	142, 86,6
	Extended	22, 13,4
Relationship with family	Good	124, 75,6
	Not bad	40, 24,4
Financial status	Good	40, 24,4
	Not bad	116, 70,7
	Bad	8, 4,9
Chronic disease	No	106, 64,6
	Yes	58, 35,4
Physical Health	Good	78, 47,6
	Not bad	86, 52,4
Mental Health	Good	82, 50,0
	Not bad	70, 42,7
	Bad	12, 7,3
Leisure Activities	Walking	18, 11,0
	Spend time with family	16, 9,8
	Reading book	62, 37,8
	Resting	32, 19,5
	Watching TV	8, 4,9
	Hobby activity	28, 17,1

The mean total Health Anxiety Scale (HAS) score of the participants was 14.29 ± 6.45 . With respect to the subdimensions of health anxiety, the mean score for bodily vigilance was 11.33 ± 5.06 , whereas the mean score for negative consequences of illness was 2.96 ± 2.06 .

The mean total score of the Holistic Complementary and Alternative Medicine Questionnaire (HCAHQ) was 28.96 ± 8.42 . The mean score for the holistic health beliefs subscale was 10.22 ± 5.66 , and the mean score for the CAM orientation subscale was 18.74 ± 4.97 (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean Scores of Age, Health Anxiety, Total CAM Attitudes, and Their Subscales

	Mean \pm SD	Median (Min-Max)
Health Anxiety Total	$14,29 \pm 6,45$	13 (2 - 37)
Sensitivity to Bodily Symptoms	$11,33 \pm 5,06$	10 (2 - 30)
Negative Outcomes of Illness	$2,96 \pm 2,06$	3 (0 - 7)
CAM Total	$28,96 \pm 8,42$	27 (15 - 56)
Holistic Health Total	$10,22 \pm 5,66$	8 (5 - 25)
CAM Orientation	$18,74 \pm 4,97$	18 (10 - 31)
Age	$35,7 \pm 8,85$	35 (20 - 61)

Health anxiety and bodily vigilance scores differed significantly according to education level ($p < .05$). High school graduates had lower health anxiety scores compared to other groups, whereas university graduates demonstrated the highest mean scores. No significant differences were observed in the negative consequences of illness subscale, total CAM score, holistic health beliefs, or CAM orientation across education levels.

With respect to perceived economic status, a significant difference was found only in the negative consequences of illness subscale ($p = .021$). Participants reporting poor economic status had lower scores on this subdimension compared to those in other economic groups.

Significant differences were observed across all scale scores according to perceived mental health status ($p < .001$). Participants who rated their mental health as poor had the highest scores in total health anxiety and its subdimensions. Similarly, individuals with poor perceived mental health demonstrated higher total CAM, holistic health beliefs, and CAM orientation scores compared to other groups.

Regarding perceived physical health, participants who rated their physical health as

good had significantly lower scores in total health anxiety ($p < .001$), bodily vigilance ($p < .001$), and negative consequences of illness ($p = .018$) compared to those reporting moderate physical health. However, no significant differences were found in total CAM scores or its subdimensions.

Family relationship quality was significantly associated with total health anxiety ($p = .020$) and bodily vigilance ($p = .008$). Participants reporting good family relationships had lower

scores in these domains compared to those indicating moderate family relationships.

Leisure activities were significantly associated with the negative consequences of illness subscale ($p = .001$). In particular, individuals who preferred resting or watching television reported higher scores in this dimension compared to other activity groups. Significant differences were also observed for total health anxiety ($p = .042$) and holistic health beliefs ($p = .028$). No significant differences were detected in the remaining subscales.

Table 3. Comparison of Mean Scale Scores Across Selected Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics		Health Anxiety Total	Sensitivity to Bodily Symptoms	Negative Outcomes of Illness	CAM Total	Holistic Health Total	Orientation
Education status	Primary education	14,5 ± 5,98	11,25 ± 4,43	3,25 ± 2,31	29,5 ± 9,12	11,25 ± 4,56	18,25 ± 4,56
	High school	11,31 ± 5,44	8,63 ± 4,14	2,69 ± 1,99	26,75 ± 8,53	9,31 ± 5,32	17,44 ± 4,98
	University	15,05 ± 6,54	12,03 ± 5,11	3,02 ± 2,08	29,5 ± 8,33	10,39 ± 5,81	19,11 ± 4,97
	F	4.545	6.133	0.401	1.379	0.596	1.498
	p	0.013	0.003	0.670	0.255	0.552	0.227
Financial status	Good	15,05 ± 8,16	12,05 ± 6,34	3 ± 2,26	28,75 ± 11,05	10,85 ± 6,48	17,9 ± 5,41
	Not bad	14,31 ± 5,88	11,22 ± 4,67	3,09 ± 1,99	28,9 ± 7,56	9,98 ± 5,48	18,91 ± 4,85
	Bad	10,25 ± 2,76	9,25 ± 2,43	1 ± 1,07	31 ± 5,29	10,5 ± 3,89	20,5 ± 4,11
	F	1.868	1.108	3.975	0.248	0.357	1.148
	p	0.158	0.333	0.021	0.781	0.700	0.320
Mental health	Good	11,22 ± 3,97	8,83 ± 3,02	2,39 ± 1,75	28,17 ± 8,53	10,24 ± 5,87	17,93 ± 5,04
	Not bad	16,06 ± 5,87	12,97 ± 4,64	3,09 ± 1,92	28 ± 7,4	8,77 ± 3,9	19,23 ± 5,06
	Bad	25 ± 8,29	18,83 ± 7,2	6,17 ± 1,95	40 ± 5,26	18,5 ± 6,05	21,5 ± 1,57
	F.	27.948	27.650	22.417	12.725	29.449	64.076
	p	p<0.001	p<0.001	p<0.001	p<0.001	p<0.001	p<0.001
Physical health	Good	12,03 ± 4,79	9,46 ± 3,5	2,56 ± 1,94	29,36 ± 8,34	10,87 ± 6,02	18,49 ± 4,75
	Not bad	16,35 ± 7,07	13,02 ± 5,65	3,33 ± 2,11	28,6 ± 8,53	9,63 ± 5,27	18,98 ± 5,17
	t	4.621	4.903	2.395	0.572	1.411	0.629
	p	p<0.001	p<0.001	0.018	0.568	0.160	0.530
	Relationship with family	Good	13,63 ± 6,71	10,74 ± 5,13	2,89 ± 2,16	29,13 ± 8,83	10,69 ± 6,04
Not bad		16,35 ± 5,09	13,15 ± 4,41	3,2 ± 1,74	28,45 ± 7,1	8,75 ± 3,95	19,7 ± 4,59
t		2.353	2.666	0.833	0.422	1.905	1.405
p		0.020	0.008	0.406	0.659	0.059	0.162
Leisure Activities		Walking	14,22 ± 6,7	11,33 ± 5,64	2,89 ± 1,97	28,33 ± 9,68	9,67 ± 7,67
	end time with family	13 ± 3,9	10,75 ± 4,06	2,25 ± 1,24	26,13 ± 6,72	7,88 ± 2,39	18,25 ± 5,88
	Reading book	12,84 ± 5,77	10,32 ± 4,39	2,52 ± 1,86	29,52 ± 8,86	10,97 ± 5,69	18,55 ± 4,72
	Resting	17,13 ± 8,72	12,81 ± 6,89	4,31 ± 2,29	31,81 ± 9,83	12,25 ± 6,93	19,56 ± 5,3
	Watching TV	17 ± 7,48	13,5 ± 5,78	3,5 ± 2,88	28,75 ± 5,42	7 ± 2,14	21,75 ± 5,73
	Sporty activity	14,29 ± 4,45	11,57 ± 3,46	2,71 ± 1,82	26,57 ± 5,22	8,86 ± 2,98	17,71 ± 4,26
	F	2.372	1.408	4.290	1.655	2.589	1.055
	p	0.042	0.224	0.001	0.149	0.028	0.388

The correlations between total CAM score, CAM orientation, holistic health beliefs, and the subdimensions of health anxiety are presented in Table 4. Examination of the table indicates a strong and statistically significant negative correlation between the total CAM score and total health anxiety score. Similarly, a moderate-to-strong negative correlation was observed between holistic health beliefs and total health anxiety. The CAM orientation subscale demonstrated a very strong negative correlation with total health anxiety.

Given that lower scores on the CAM scale reflect more positive attitudes toward CAM, these findings indicate that individuals with lower total CAM, holistic health, and CAM orientation scores tend to exhibit higher levels of health anxiety. In other words, as health anxiety increases, positive attitudes toward and orientation to complementary and alternative medicine also increase.

Table 4. Correlations Between Participants' Mean Scale Scores

		CAM Total	Holistic Health Total	CAM Orientation
Health Anxiety Total	r	-0,812	-0,664	-0,927
	p	0,019	0,034	0,007
Sensitivity to Bodily Symptoms	r	-0,301	-0,527	-0,302
	p	0,081	0,050	0,081
Negative Outcomes of Illness	r	-0,141	-0,848	-0,221
	p	0,073	0,015	0,004

DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationship between health anxiety and attitudes toward complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) among adults attending a university hospital and revealed a strong and statistically significant association between these variables. The findings indicate that higher levels of health anxiety are associated with more favorable attitudes toward and greater orientation to CAM. Given that lower CAM scale scores reflect more positive attitudes, the strong negative correlations observed ($r = -.812$; $r = -.927$) represent a clinically meaningful pattern. These results suggest that individuals with elevated health anxiety may engage in greater control-seeking behaviors in response to perceived health threats and, consequently, turn to treatment options beyond the conventional biomedical system.

According to cognitive-behavioral models, health anxiety is maintained by threat-focused misinterpretations of bodily sensations and by safety-seeking behaviors (2, 3). From this perspective, orientation toward CAM may function as a form of safety-seeking behavior. The particularly strong association between the “negative consequences of illness” subdimension and holistic health beliefs ($r = -.848$) is noteworthy. This finding suggests that catastrophic cognitions concerning death, disability, or disease progression may lead individuals to prefer treatment modalities perceived as more holistic and controllable. Previous research has shown that individuals with chronic illnesses or medically unexplained symptoms are more likely to use CAM (11, 12). The present findings extend this literature by indicating that CAM orientation may be driven

not only by physical illness but also by cognitive threat appraisal processes.

The significant differences observed across all scale scores according to perceived mental health status ($p < .001$) constitute one of the strongest findings of this study. Participants reporting poor mental health demonstrated the highest levels of health anxiety as well as the highest CAM orientation scores. This pattern suggests a link between psychological vulnerability and alternative health-seeking behaviors. Previous studies indicate that symptoms of anxiety and depression are associated with increased CAM use (10). CAM may therefore serve not only as a means of addressing physical concerns but also as a strategy for emotional regulation, reassurance, and meaning-making. In cultural contexts such as Türkiye, where practices such as prayer, cupping therapy, and herbal remedies hold both cultural and spiritual significance, this tendency may be further reinforced.

The finding that university graduates exhibited higher health anxiety scores is particularly noteworthy. Although lower educational attainment is often associated with limited health literacy, the reverse pattern observed in this study may reflect greater exposure to online health information among highly educated individuals. Increased access to digital health content may contribute to cyberchondria and heightened threat perception (4). Thus, greater information access does not necessarily reduce anxiety; in some cases, it may amplify uncertainty and catastrophic interpretations.

Consistent with the social support literature, better family relationships were associated with lower health anxiety levels. Social support may function as a protective buffer, reducing perceived threat and limiting reassurance-seeking behaviors. Similarly, participants reporting good physical health demonstrated lower health anxiety scores, which aligns with theoretical expectations. However, the absence of significant differences in CAM attitudes according to physical health suggests that CAM orientation may be more strongly linked to psychological rather than somatic factors.

The finding that individuals who preferred passive leisure activities such as resting or watching television reported higher “negative consequences of illness” scores may indicate an

association between passive coping styles and heightened threat appraisal. Future research should investigate the potential mediating role of coping styles in the relationship between health anxiety and CAM orientation.

Overall, the findings suggest that the relationship between health anxiety and CAM orientation is not solely attributable to cultural or sociodemographic variables but is closely associated with cognitive threat appraisal, psychological vulnerability, and control-seeking tendencies. These results support a holistic interpretation of CAM use as a coping strategy for managing uncertainty rather than as a purely irrational or pathological behavior.

Limitations: Several methodological limitations should be acknowledged. First, due to the cross-sectional design, causal inferences cannot be established. It remains unclear whether health anxiety leads to increased CAM orientation or whether CAM engagement influences anxiety levels. Second, the sample was drawn from a single university hospital, which limits the generalizability of the findings. Third, the predominance of female and university-educated participants reduces sample heterogeneity. Fourth, data were collected through self-report measures, introducing the possibility of social desirability bias and measurement error. Finally, although attitudes toward CAM were assessed, actual frequency and types of CAM use were not examined in detail.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated a strong association between health anxiety and attitudes toward complementary and alternative medicine (CAM). The findings suggest that individuals with higher psychological vulnerability and stronger cognitive threat appraisals regarding the negative consequences of illness are more likely to exhibit greater orientation toward CAM.

From a clinical perspective, healthcare professionals should incorporate routine assessment of CAM use and attitudes into the evaluation process of individuals with elevated health anxiety. Psychoeducational interventions should specifically target maladaptive cognitive distortions and safety-seeking behaviors that maintain health-related anxiety. Additionally, patients should be provided with evidence-

based guidance regarding the potential risks and benefits of CAM modalities to support informed decision-making.

With respect to future research, longitudinal studies are needed to clarify causal relationships between health anxiety and CAM orientation. The potential mediating or moderating roles of cyberchondria, health literacy, and coping styles should be systematically examined. Furthermore, qualitative research employing phenomenological approaches may help to elucidate the subjective meaning and experiential dimensions of CAM orientation. Cross-cultural comparative studies would also contribute to a deeper understanding of how sociocultural contexts shape the relationship between health anxiety and alternative health-seeking behaviors.

In conclusion, health anxiety should not be conceptualized solely as an internal psychological process; it also shapes individuals' engagement with healthcare systems and their pursuit of alternative treatment options. Accordingly, healthcare services should adopt a more integrative framework that combines biomedical and psychosocial perspectives in order to address patients' needs comprehensively.

DESCRIPTIONS

No financial support.

No conflict of interest.

Ethics committee approval: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of Harran University with the approval number E-76244175-050.01.01-172343. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

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